

Report on the fourth needs analysis results

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The fourth needs analysis results concerning “Sustainable and responsible innovation supported by academia to business collaboration”

Need analysis represents the part of the researchers’ activities that follow the return phase, together with Focus group and Delphi study. Precisely, after each secondment to EU non-academic partner, upon returning to their home country, talents present the key issues and ideas from secondment phase and, together with researchers identify the situation and assess the needs of the business community in each widening country. For this, focus groups, needs analysis, Delphi study, systematic literature research and alike will be conducted.

Specific skills that should be gained during the secondments to EU countries are by far the most important soft element of Centers for entrepreneurship and innovation (EI centers), which will be established at each widening academic institution. Those skills represent EI centers core area, as a tool to create a bridge between academic institutions and business community. A combination of the right secondments and a return phase at the widening sending institution aims at (1) providing additional knowledge and skills (during the secondments) and (2) adapting this knowledge to the specific, local and national entrepreneurial ecosystem (e.g. while conducting systematic literature research, focus groups, Delphi study, needs analysis and alike).

Needs analysis is aimed at getting information about sustainable and responsible innovation, innovation process management and A2B cooperation’s importance from the business community point of view. It is based on the questionnaire, which was produced as the result of the Delphi study. During period October – November 2024, questionnaire was formulated and then used for collecting data. Data were collected in all four widening countries: Serbia, Albania, Bosnia & Herzegovina, North Macedonia.

Needs analysis should point out the most important phases and tools of innovation process management. It should also clarify the difference between sustainable and responsible innovation and how A2B cooperation can support these kinds of innovations, and finally how impact of this cooperation can be measured and monitored.

The idea is to use the analysis results to decide which tools and measures are the least present and the most needed by the business community so have to be included into the training programme that will be composed under each Center for entrepreneurship and innovation (EI centers).

Sample structure

Research refers to the sample of 100 companies. In each widening country were collected 25 questionnaires. The following table describe the sample according to company size in each country.

Table 1: Number of companies per country

		Company size			Total
		Large	Medium	Small	
Country	Albania	4	8	13	25
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	5	5	15	25
	North Macedonia	5	8	12	25

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	Serbia	13	5	7	25
	Total	27	26	47	100

Source: Authors' presentation

The majority of the companies in the sample are small (47), followed by large (27) and medium (26).

Table 2: Company size

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Large	27	27.0	27.0
	Medium	26	26.0	53.0
	Small	47	47.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Source: Authors' presentation

Taking into account the company's activities, the largest participation in the sample have companies from the fields of Information and Communications (22%), Other service activities (17%) and Manufacturing Industry (12%).

Table 3: Company's activity

Activity	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Area B: Extraction of ores and stone	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
Area C: Manufacturing industry	12	12.0	12.0	13.0
Area D: Production and supply of electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning	3	3.0	3.0	16.0
Area E: Water supply, sewage, waste management and environmental remediation activities	2	2.0	2.0	18.0
Area F: Construction	2	2.0	2.0	20.0
Area G: Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	1	1.0	1.0	21.0
Area H: Transportation and storage	1	1.0	1.0	22.0
Area I: Activities of providing accommodation, preparing and serving food, hotel and catering	1	1.0	1.0	23.0
Area J: Information and communication	5	5.0	5.0	28.0
Area J: Information and Communications	22	22.0	22.0	50.0
Area K: Financial and insurance activities	8	8.0	8.0	58.0
Area M: Professional, scientific and technical activities	8	8.0	8.0	66.0
Area N: Administrative and auxiliary service activities	2	2.0	2.0	68.0

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Area O: Public administration and defence, compulsory social insurance	2	2.0	2.0	70.0
Area P: Education	9	9.0	9.0	79.0
Area R: Arts, entertainment and recreation	2	2.0	2.0	81.0
Area S: Other service activities	17	17.0	17.0	98.0
Area T: Activities of households as employers; household activities that produce various goods and perform various services for personal use	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Authors' presentation

Considering the gender, for the largest number of the companies' respondents were men, in 67% of cases.

Table 4: Gender structure of respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	33	33.0	33.0	33.0
	Male	67	67.0	67.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Authors' presentation

The largest percentage of respondents have Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - social and humanities (25%), followed by Higher professional education - III cycle of studies - social and humanities (15%), Higher professional education - I cycle of studies - social and humanities (13%), and Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - technical sciences (11%). Only 8% of managers in the sample have Secondary education.

Table 5: Respondent's education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Higher professional education - I cycle of studies - technical sciences	10	10.0	10.0	10.0
	Higher professional education - I cycle of studies - natural sciences	1	1.0	1.0	11.0
	Higher professional education - I cycle of studies - social and humanities	13	13.0	13.0	24.0
	Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - technical sciences	11	11.0	11.0	35.0
	Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - natural sciences	8	8.0	8.0	43.0

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Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - social and humanities	25	25.0	25.0	68.0
Higher professional education - III cycle of studies - natural sciences	4	4.0	4.0	72.0
Higher professional education - III cycle of studies - social and humanities	15	15.0	15.0	87.0
Higher professional education - III cycle of studies - technical sciences	5	5.0	5.0	92.0
Secondary education	8	8.0	8.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Authors' presentation

Statistical analysis

According to the research results and descriptive statistical analysis (Table), all tested variables were rated very high. The average rating of all is higher than 4, except: 2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [d] government] (3.83), 4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [b] business model canvas] (3.96), 5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [f] positive economic impact] (4.32), 11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [b] social impact] (3.95), 12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [a] number of start-ups] (3.87), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [a] pollution control, waste reduction, and recycling] (3.96), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [b] energy efficiency and renewable energy] (3.99), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [d] social inclusion and ethical practices] (3.81), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [e] public transport improvement and emission reduction] (3.97), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [f] climate action] (3.76).

The highest average ratings achieved for the following variables: 1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [b] collaboration and knowledge sharing] (4.60), 2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [i] innovative companies] (4.61), 3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [h] feedback analysis] (4.68), 9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [b] companies] (4.60). In this regard, the conclusion is that all variables are extremely important, as well as that the right variables were selected during the design of the survey questionnaire. The greatest

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disagreements, or the highest standard deviation, were recorded for the variables that were simultaneously the lowest rated by the managers.

Table 6: Descriptive statistics of tested variables

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [a] flexibility and adaptability]	100	4.5000	.79772
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [b] collaboration and knowledge sharing]	100	4.6000	.72474
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [c] supportive policy and innovation culture]	100	4.3600	.89352
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [d] creativity and multidisciplinary approach]	100	4.4700	.82211
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [e] global connectivity]	100	4.3300	.84154
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [f] cooperation among stakeholders]	100	4.3400	.83145
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [g] systematic financial support]	100	4.2700	.98324
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [a] start-ups]	100	4.2100	.89098
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [b] investors]	100	4.5300	.78438
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [c] academia]	99	4.0101	.89779
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [d] government]	100	3.8300	1.10147
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [e] accelerators]	100	4.0200	1.04427
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [f] R&D centers]	100	4.1500	.95743
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [g] entrepreneurs]	100	4.4300	.87911
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [h] industry leaders]	100	4.2900	.82014
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [i] innovative companies]	100	4.6100	.69479
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [a] opportunity identification]	100	4.5600	.64071

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3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [b] market research]	100	4.4500	.74366
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [c] idea generation and evaluation]	100	4.2800	.86550
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [d] concept development]	100	4.4200	.80629
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [e] prototyping]	100	4.3300	.75284
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [f] testing]	100	4.4300	.76877
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [g] launching]	100	4.4300	.72829
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [h] feedback analysis]	100	4.6800	.60101
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [a] design thinking]	100	4.2300	.86287
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [b] business model canvas]	100	3.9600	.85185
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [c] rapid prototyping]	100	4.0500	.83333
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [d] brainstorming]	100	4.3400	.85540
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [e] market research]	100	4.4800	.78470
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [f] MVP testing]	100	4.2900	.86801
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [g] simulations]	100	4.2400	.88899
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [a] resource efficiency and renewable resources]	100	4.1100	1.01399
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [b] minimal waste and circular economy]	100	4.0000	1.05409
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [c] environmental responsibility and social impact]	100	4.1100	.99387
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [d] adaptability]	100	4.4200	.81872
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [e] green technologies and emission reduction]	100	3.9300	1.11242
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [f] positive economic impact]	100	4.3200	.82731
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [a] ethical principles]	100	4.1800	.92529
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [b] transparency and inclusiveness]	100	4.1200	.96693

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6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [c) social accountability]	100	4.1700	.92174
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [d) long-term societal benefits]	100	4.3500	.88048
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [e) community engagement]	100	4.0100	.95869
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [f) minimizing negative impacts]	100	4.1900	.92872
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [a) lack of infrastructure]	100	4.3400	.79417
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [b) lack of financing]	100	4.4500	.75712
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [c) lack of public awareness]	100	4.1700	.94340
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [d) regulatory barriers and complex regulations]	100	4.3100	.89550
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [e) weak global market connections]	100	4.3400	.80679
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [f) lack of entrepreneurial culture]	100	4.2600	.88329
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [a) joint research projects]	100	4.1500	.88048
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [b) knowledge transfer and shared education]	100	4.4000	.85280
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [student internships]	100	4.1200	.93506
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [c) skill improvement]	100	4.3800	.81377
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [d) leveraging research capacities]	100	4.3100	.81271
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [e) market connections]	100	4.3300	.79207
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [f) technological solutions]	100	4.3800	.86199
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [g) innovative programs]	100	4.4200	.91210
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [a) universities]	100	4.2400	.99615
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [b) companies]	100	4.6000	.77850

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9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [c] innovation hubs]	100	4.2800	.89983
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [d] accelerators]	100	4.1500	1.02863
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [e] policymakers]	100	4.0900	1.10184
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [a] clear strategy]	100	4.3900	.79003
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [b] intellectual property management]	100	4.0400	.87525
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [c] transparency]	100	4.2121	1.00278
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [d] educational programs]	100	4.3200	.78983
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [e] innovation culture]	100	4.5000	.73168
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [f] research incubators]	100	4.2600	.89465
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [g] long-term vision]	100	4.4700	.78438
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [a] legal regulations]	100	4.0700	1.02745
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [b] social impact]	100	3.9500	.92524
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [c] innovation capacity]	100	4.2800	.80503
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [d] trust]	100	4.3300	.84154
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [e] government incentives]	100	4.0202	.98954
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [f] education]	100	4.3700	.86053
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [g] transparent communication]	100	4.3700	.78695

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11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [h] infrastructure]	100	4.4400	.74291
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [a] number of start-ups]	100	3.8700	1.00156
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [b] attracted investments]	100	4.2500	.88048
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [c] jobs created]	100	4.2800	.86550
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [d] number of innovations]	100	4.1500	.92524
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [e] financial KPIs]	100	4.1200	.84423
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [f] market readiness]	100	4.3000	.83485
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [g] start-up revenues]	100	4.0500	.95743
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [h] number of new business models]	100	4.0404	.94674
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [a] pollution control, waste reduction, and recycling]	100	3.9600	1.16272
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [b] energy efficiency and renewable energy]	100	3.9900	1.08707
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually	100	4.0100	1.02981

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tackles in your country? [c] sustainable agriculture and biodiversity conservation]			
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [d] social inclusion and ethical practices]	100	3.8100	1.06073
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [e] public transport improvement and emission reduction]	100	3.9700	1.08670
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [f] climate action]	100	3.7600	1.25626
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [g] education for sustainability]	100	4.1800	1.05773

Source: Authors' presentation

Taking into account the size of the company and the average ratings of the analysed variables, it can be concluded that all variables are very important regardless of the size of the company since average ratings in most cases are greater than 4. For large companies, the most significant are the following options: 1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [b] collaboration and knowledge sharing] (4.59), 2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [i] innovative companies] (4.67), 3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [e] prototyping] (4.18). The least important for this group are the following options: 2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [d] government] (3.81), 4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [c] rapid prototyping] (3.70), 12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [a] number of start-ups] (3.78).

For the medium companies the most significant are the following options: 1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [b] collaboration and knowledge sharing] (4.77), 1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [c] supportive policy and innovation culture] (4.61), 3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [f] testing] (4.50). The least important for this group are the following options: 11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [a] legal regulations] (3.88), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [f] climate action] (3.50), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [g] education for sustainability] (3.81).

Finally, small companies as the most significant find the following options: 3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [a] opportunity identification] (4.55), 3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [f] testing] (4.34), 7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [b] lack of financing] (4.55). The least important for this group are the following options: 5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [b] minimal waste and

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circular economy] (3.83), 5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [e] green technologies and emission reduction] (3.74), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [f] climate action] (3.77).

Table 7: Average ratings by company size

Company size	Large		Medium		Small	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [a] flexibility and adaptability]	4.2963	.86890	4.6538	.68948	4.5319	.80355
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [b] collaboration and knowledge sharing]	4.5926	.69389	4.7692	.51441	4.5106	.83072
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [c] supportive policy and innovation culture]	4.3333	.87706	4.6154	.49614	4.2340	1.04700
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [d] creativity and multidisciplinary approach]	4.4815	.70002	4.5769	.64331	4.4043	.97042
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [e] global connectivity]	4.4074	.74726	4.5769	.75753	4.1489	.90838
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [f] cooperation among stakeholders]	4.3704	.79169	4.3846	.75243	4.2979	.90686
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [g] systematic financial support]	4.4444	.75107	4.3846	1.06120	4.1064	1.04744

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2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [a] start-ups]	4.1481	.86397	4.2692	.91903	4.2128	.90737
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [b] investors]	4.4074	1.00992	4.6538	.62880	4.5319	.71782
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [c] academia]	3.9615	.95836	4.0000	.80000	4.0426	.93151
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [d] government]	3.8148	1.11068	4.0385	.95836	3.7234	1.17403
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [e] accelerators]	3.9259	1.14105	4.3462	.74524	3.8936	1.10796
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [f] R&D centers]	4.0000	1.14354	4.2308	.86291	4.1915	.90020
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [g] entrepreneurs]	4.2222	1.18754	4.5385	.64689	4.4894	.77662
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [h] industry leaders]	4.3333	.87706	4.5000	.64807	4.1489	.85919
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [i] innovative companies]	4.6667	.73380	4.7692	.42967	4.4894	.77662
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [a] opportunity identification]	4.3704	.74152	4.7692	.51441	4.5532	.61885
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [b] market research]	4.3333	.78446	4.7308	.60383	4.3617	.76401
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [c] idea generation and evaluation]	4.2963	.82345	4.5000	.86023	4.1489	.88413

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3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [d] concept development]	4.4074	.88835	4.5769	.64331	4.3404	.84124
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [e] prototyping]	4.1852	.83376	4.5385	.70602	4.2979	.71975
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [f] testing]	4.5185	.89315	4.5000	.70711	4.3404	.73059
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [g] launching]	4.4074	.84395	4.4231	.75753	4.4468	.65304
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [h] feedback analysis]	4.6296	.68770	4.7692	.51441	4.6596	.59988
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [a] design thinking]	4.0741	1.07152	4.2692	.87442	4.2979	.71975
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [b] business model canvas]	3.9259	.87380	4.0000	.89443	3.9574	.83295
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [c] rapid prototyping]	3.7037	.91209	4.3077	.78838	4.1064	.75855
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [d] brainstorming]	4.4074	.88835	4.5385	.70602	4.1915	.90020
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [e] market research]	4.3333	.96077	4.7308	.45234	4.4255	.80067
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [f] MVP testing]	4.2963	.91209	4.3846	.89786	4.2340	.83958

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4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [g] simulations]	4.1481	.94883	4.2692	.87442	4.2766	.87730
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [a] resource efficiency and renewable resources]	3.8889	1.15470	4.4231	.90213	4.0638	.96469
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [b] minimal waste and circular economy]	3.9630	1.15962	4.3462	.89184	3.8298	1.04921
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [c] environmental responsibility and social impact]	4.2222	1.18754	4.3462	.74524	3.9149	.97423
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [d] adaptability]	4.2593	.94432	4.4615	.70602	4.4894	.80413
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [e] green technologies and emission reduction]	4.1111	1.15470	4.0769	1.05539	3.7447	1.11254
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [f] positive economic impact]	4.3333	.96077	4.4231	.64331	4.2553	.84617
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [a] ethical principles]	4.0370	1.01835	4.3462	.79711	4.1702	.93992
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [b] transparency and inclusiveness]	4.1481	1.06351	4.1154	.86380	4.1064	.98321
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [c] social accountability]	4.2593	.98421	4.1154	.86380	4.1489	.93201
6. How significant are the following characteristics of	4.4074	1.00992	4.3077	.78838	4.3404	.86669

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responsible innovation? [d] long-term societal benefits]						
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [e] community engagement]	4.0370	1.09128	3.9615	.87090	4.0213	.94384
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [f] minimizing negative impacts]	4.2593	1.02254	4.1538	.88056	4.1702	.91649
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [a] lack of infrastructure]	4.1111	.93370	4.5000	.76158	4.3830	.70874
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [b] lack of financing]	4.2593	.94432	4.4615	.76057	4.5532	.61885
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [c] lack of public awareness]	4.0741	.99715	4.1923	.84943	4.2128	.97660
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [d] regulatory barriers and complex regulations]	4.3333	.96077	4.2692	.87442	4.3191	.88726
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [e] weak global market connections]	4.1852	.92141	4.3846	.75243	4.4043	.77065
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [f] lack of entrepreneurial culture]	4.0741	.91676	4.1538	.73170	4.4255	.92653
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [a] joint research projects]	4.0370	.93978	4.2692	.87442	4.1489	.85919

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8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [b) knowledge transfer and shared education]	4.4074	.97109	4.2308	.95111	4.4894	.71846
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [student internships]	4.0741	1.10683	4.1923	.84943	4.1064	.89038
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [c) skill improvement]	4.4815	.84900	4.4615	.64689	4.2766	.87730
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [d) leveraging research capacities]	4.1481	.94883	4.4615	.76057	4.3191	.75488
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [e) market connections]	4.1111	.89156	4.5000	.70711	4.3617	.76401
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [f) technological solutions]	4.4444	.93370	4.5000	.81240	4.2766	.85216
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [g) innovative programs]	4.3704	1.21365	4.4231	.75753	4.4468	.80240
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [a) universities]	4.0000	1.17670	4.3846	.85215	4.2979	.95359
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [b) companies]	4.5185	.84900	4.6923	.67937	4.5957	.79836
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [c) innovation hubs]	4.3704	.83887	4.3846	.69725	4.1702	1.02828
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [d) accelerators]	4.1111	1.01274	4.3846	.69725	4.0426	1.17875
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [e) policymakers]	4.2222	.97402	4.1154	1.07059	4.0000	1.19782
10. How significant are the following elements for	4.2593	.94432	4.3846	.75243	4.4681	.71782

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establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [a] clear strategy]						
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [b] intellectual property management]	4.0000	.91987	4.1154	.76561	4.0213	.92052
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [c] transparency]	4.1481	1.23113	4.1600	.74610	4.2766	.99350
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [d] educational programs]	4.2593	.98421	4.3077	.78838	4.3617	.67326
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [e] innovation culture]	4.4074	.88835	4.6154	.69725	4.4894	.65516
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [f] research incubators]	4.1111	1.05003	4.3462	.79711	4.2979	.85757
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [g] long-term vision]	4.4074	.93064	4.4615	.70602	4.5106	.74811
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [a] legal regulations]	4.2593	1.02254	3.8846	1.14287	4.0638	.96469
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [b] social impact]	4.1111	.84732	3.9231	.97665	3.8723	.94678
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B	4.2963	.91209	4.3077	.73589	4.2553	.79312

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collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [c] innovation capacity]						
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [d] trust]	4.2593	.94432	4.5000	.81240	4.2766	.79951
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [e] government incentives]	4.0000	.96077	4.0769	.97665	4.0000	1.03280
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [f] education]	4.2222	1.05003	4.5385	.70602	4.3617	.81895
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [g] transparent communication]	4.4074	.97109	4.3846	.69725	4.3404	.73059
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [h] infrastructure]	4.4815	.84900	4.3846	.75243	4.4468	.68552
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [a] number of start-ups]	3.7778	1.21950	3.9615	.87090	3.8723	.94678
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [b] attracted investments]	4.0000	1.00000	4.3462	.74524	4.3404	.86669
12. How significant are the following indicators for	4.4074	.93064	4.2692	.72430	4.2128	.90737

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assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [c] jobs created]						
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [d] number of innovations]	4.1111	.97402	4.2692	.82741	4.1064	.96084
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [e] financial KPIs]	4.0370	.97985	4.1538	.78446	4.1489	.80700
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [f] market readiness]	4.2222	.97402	4.3462	.68948	4.3191	.83683
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [g] start-up revenues]	4.0741	.99715	4.0769	.84489	4.0213	1.01058
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [h]	4.0741	1.03500	4.0385	.72004	4.0217	1.02174

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number of new business models]						
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [a] pollution control, waste reduction, and recycling]	3.8889	1.21950	4.0000	1.20000	3.9787	1.13232
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [b] energy efficiency and renewable energy]	3.8889	1.05003	4.0385	1.18257	4.0213	1.07318
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [c] sustainable agriculture and biodiversity conservation]	3.7778	1.18754	3.9615	1.07632	4.1702	.89246
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [d] social inclusion and ethical practices]	3.8519	1.13353	3.6538	1.05612	3.8723	1.03456
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [e] public transport improvement and emission reduction]	3.8889	1.31071	3.8846	1.07059	4.0638	.96469
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible	4.0000	1.14354	3.5000	1.42127	3.7660	1.21964

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innovation usually tackles in your country? [f] climate action]						
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [g] education for sustainability]	4.2222	1.08604	3.8077	1.26552	4.3617	.87042

Source: Authors' presentation

Previous results and the analysis of the average ratings of the variables achieved by country, shows enviable results, since in most cases in the analysed countries the average ratings are above 4. The differences by the countries are analysed and presented in the next table. The lowest rated variables in Albania are: 5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [b] minimal waste and circular economy] (3.76), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [b] energy efficiency and renewable energy] (3.64), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [d] social inclusion and ethical practices] (3.64).

Managers in Bosnia and Herzegovina the lowest marks gave to the following options: 5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [e] green technologies and emission reduction] (3.48), 6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [e] community engagement] (3.68), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [f] climate action] (3.44).

The lowest marks in North Macedonia are for variables: 2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [d] government] (3.72), 11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [a] legal regulations] (3.76), 11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [e] government incentives] (3.76).

In Serbia, the lowest marks were given to variables: 4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [a] design thinking] (3.76), 12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [a] number of start-ups] (3.76), 13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [f] climate action] (3.80).

Table 8: Average ratings by country

Country	Albania		Bosnia and Herzegovina		North Macedonia		Serbia	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. How significant are the following characteristics for	4.5600	.65064	4.6000	.86603	4.5200	.58595	4.3200	1.02956

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a successful innovation ecosystem? [a] flexibility and adaptability]									
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [b] collaboration and knowledge sharing]	4.5200	.65320	4.6000	.91287	4.7200	.54160	4.5600	.76811	
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [c] supportive policy and innovation culture]	4.2800	.73711	4.0000	1.22474	4.6400	.56862	4.5200	.82260	
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [d] creativity and multidisciplinary approach]	4.4000	.95743	4.4800	.91833	4.5200	.65320	4.4800	.77028	
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [e] global connectivity]	4.4000	.76376	4.3600	.86023	4.4000	.76376	4.1600	.98658	
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [f]	4.4800	.65320	4.4000	.95743	4.2400	.66332	4.2400	1.01160	

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cooperation among stakeholders]								
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [g] systematic financial support]	4.3600	.75719	4.2400	1.09087	4.2400	1.05198	4.2400	1.05198
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [a] start-ups]	4.1200	.88129	4.1200	1.01325	4.5200	.50990	4.0800	1.03763
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [b] investors]	4.5600	.82057	4.6000	.70711	4.6800	.55678	4.2800	.97980
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [c] academia]	4.0000	1.02151	4.0400	.67577	4.0400	.78951	3.9600	1.09848
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [d] government]	3.6800	1.10755	3.9200	1.15181	3.7200	.97980	4.0000	1.19024
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [e] accelerators]	3.9200	1.07703	4.1600	.85049	4.0800	1.11505	3.9200	1.15181
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation	3.9600	1.13578	4.2000	.81650	4.5600	.65064	3.8800	1.05357

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ecosystem? [f] R&D centers]								
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [g] entrepreneurs]	4.4000	1.04083	4.6400	.56862	4.5600	.58310	4.1200	1.12990
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [h] industry leaders]	4.2800	.89069	4.2800	.84261	4.4000	.64550	4.2000	.91287
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [i] innovative companies]	4.4800	.77028	4.6400	.63770	4.8400	.37417	4.4800	.87178
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [a] opportunity identification]	4.5600	.65064	4.5200	.58595	4.6400	.56862	4.5200	.77028
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [b] market research]	4.3600	.81035	4.4400	.71181	4.6400	.56862	4.3600	.86023
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [c] idea generation and evaluation]	4.2000	.95743	4.1600	.94340	4.4400	.71181	4.3200	.85245

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3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [d] concept development]	4.3600	.75719	4.2800	.93630	4.6000	.64550	4.4400	.86987
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [e] prototyping]	4.2400	.66332	4.3200	.74833	4.5600	.65064	4.2000	.91287
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [f] testing]	4.4000	.70711	4.4000	.70711	4.6400	.56862	4.2800	1.02144
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [g] launching]	4.3200	.74833	4.5200	.50990	4.6800	.55678	4.2000	.95743
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [h] feedback analysis]	4.6000	.57735	4.7200	.54160	4.8000	.50000	4.6000	.76376
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [a] design thinking]	4.3600	.70000	4.3200	.62716	4.4800	.77028	3.7600	1.12842
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in	3.8800	.83267	3.8000	.81650	4.2400	.77889	3.9200	.95394

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business practice? [b] business model canvas]								
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [c] rapid prototyping]	4.2400	.77889	4.0400	.78951	4.0400	.73485	3.8800	1.01325
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [d] brainstorming]	3.9200	.99666	4.5600	.65064	4.4400	.71181	4.4400	.91652
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [e] market research]	4.2400	.87939	4.4000	.76376	4.7200	.54160	4.5600	.86987
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [f] MVP testing]	4.3600	.86023	4.4000	.64550	4.3200	.74833	4.0800	1.15181
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [g] simulations]	4.4000	.86603	4.0000	.81650	4.3600	.75719	4.2000	1.08012
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [a] resource efficiency and renewable resources]	4.0400	1.01980	3.9200	1.03763	4.5200	.65320	3.9600	1.20692
5. How significant are the following characteristics of	3.7600	1.01160	3.7200	1.06145	4.4800	.71414	4.0400	1.24097

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sustainable innovation? [b] minimal waste and circular economy]								
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [c] environmental responsibility and social impact]	4.1200	1.01325	3.8000	1.00000	4.4400	.65064	4.0800	1.18743
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [d] adaptability]	4.3200	.94516	4.4400	.71181	4.6400	.56862	4.2800	.97980
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [e] green technologies and emission reduction]	3.8400	1.14310	3.4800	1.19443	4.4800	.71414	3.9200	1.15181
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [f] positive economic impact]	4.2000	.86603	4.5600	.71181	4.3200	.55678	4.2000	1.08012
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [a] ethical principles]	4.5200	.65320	3.8000	1.04083	4.4400	.71181	3.9600	1.05987
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [b]	4.4000	.76376	3.8400	1.10604	4.1600	.85049	4.0800	1.07703

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transparency and inclusiveness]								
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [c] social accountability]	4.1200	.88129	4.0400	1.01980	4.3600	.81035	4.1600	.98658
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [d] long-term societal benefits]	4.2800	.93630	4.1200	.92736	4.6800	.55678	4.3200	.98826
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [e] community engagement]	4.0800	.90921	3.6800	1.02956	4.2000	.86603	4.0800	.99666
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [f] minimizing negative impacts]	4.1600	.85049	3.9600	1.01980	4.4400	.71181	4.2000	1.08012
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [a] lack of infrastructure]	4.1600	.74610	4.4800	.65320	4.6000	.57735	4.1200	1.05357
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [b] lack of financing]	4.3600	.70000	4.6400	.56862	4.4800	.71414	4.3200	.98826

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7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [c] lack of public awareness]	3.8000	.81650	4.4000	1.04083	4.3600	.81035	4.1200	1.01325
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [d] regulatory barriers and complex regulations]	4.0000	1.00000	4.6400	.63770	4.4800	.71414	4.1200	1.05357
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [e] weak global market connections]	4.1600	.94340	4.5600	.58310	4.5600	.58310	4.0800	.95394
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [f] lack of entrepreneurial culture]	4.2800	.89069	4.5600	.65064	4.2400	.83066	3.9600	1.05987
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [a] joint research projects]	4.0800	.90921	4.2400	.92556	4.3200	.74833	3.9600	.93452
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B	4.2400	.83066	4.5200	.77028	4.5200	.82260	4.3200	.98826

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collaboration? [b] knowledge transfer and shared education]								
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [student internships]	3.8400	.94340	4.2400	.77889	4.3600	.75719	4.0400	1.17189
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [c] skill improvement]	4.2400	.83066	4.4000	.86603	4.5200	.71414	4.3600	.86023
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [d] leveraging research capacities]	4.0800	.81240	4.4000	.76376	4.6800	.55678	4.0800	.95394
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [e] market connections]	4.3200	.85245	4.4000	.64550	4.4400	.71181	4.1600	.94340
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [f] technological solutions]	4.0800	.86217	4.6400	.63770	4.4800	.71414	4.3200	1.10755
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [g] innovative programs]	4.1200	.88129	4.6000	.57735	4.5200	1.04563	4.4400	1.04403
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [a] universities]	4.0000	1.08012	4.3600	.86023	4.5200	.87178	4.0800	1.11505

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9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [b] companies]	4.6800	.55678	4.6400	.63770	4.7200	.45826	4.3600	1.22066
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [c] innovation hubs]	4.1600	.80000	4.0400	1.05987	4.7200	.54160	4.2000	1.00000
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [d] accelerators]	4.1200	1.05357	4.0000	1.11803	4.4000	.95743	4.0800	.99666
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [e] policymakers]	4.0400	1.01980	4.0800	1.22202	4.0800	1.15181	4.1600	1.06771
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [a] clear strategy]	4.4400	.58310	4.4800	.77028	4.5200	.65320	4.1200	1.05357
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [b] intellectual property management]	4.0400	.97809	4.2800	.67823	3.9200	.75939	3.9200	1.03763
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B	4.2500	.94409	4.3200	.98826	4.1200	1.09240	4.1600	1.02794

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collaborative models? [c] transparency]									
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [d] educational programs]	4.1200	.78102	4.4800	.71414	4.4000	.64550	4.2800	.97980	
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [e] innovation culture]	4.5200	.58595	4.5600	.58310	4.7200	.54160	4.2000	1.04083	
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [f] research incubators]	4.2800	.73711	4.2000	.91287	4.5600	.71181	4.0000	1.11803	
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [g] long-term vision]	4.4400	.76811	4.6000	.50000	4.6800	.62716	4.1600	1.06771	
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration	4.1200	.88129	4.1600	1.06771	3.7600	.96954	4.2400	1.16476	

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for sustainable and responsible innovation? [a] legal regulations]								
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [b] social impact]	3.9200	.95394	3.8800	.83267	3.9600	.93452	4.0400	1.01980
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [c] innovation capacity]	4.1600	.62450	4.3600	.81035	4.6000	.50000	4.0000	1.08012
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [d] trust]	4.4000	.81650	4.4400	.71181	4.2800	.79162	4.2000	1.04083
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [e] government incentives]	4.2917	.75060	3.9200	1.15181	3.7600	.83066	4.1200	1.12990
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [f] education]	4.3600	.75719	4.3600	.75719	4.4400	.82057	4.3200	1.10755

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11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [g] transparent communication]	4.4400	.65064	4.3600	.75719	4.3600	.70000	4.3200	1.02956
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [h] infrastructure]	4.6400	.63770	4.4400	.65064	4.3200	.62716	4.3600	.99499
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [a] number of start-ups]	3.7200	.89069	4.0000	1.08012	4.0000	.91287	3.7600	1.12842
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process	4.3600	.75719	4.2800	.93630	4.4400	.71181	3.9200	1.03763

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management? [b] attracted investments]								
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [c] jobs created]	4.1600	.89815	4.4000	.76376	4.4800	.65320	4.0800	1.07703
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [d] number of innovations]	4.1200	.92736	3.9600	.93452	4.6400	.63770	3.8800	1.01325
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation	4.1200	.88129	4.2400	.72342	4.1200	.72572	4.0000	1.04083

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process management? [e] financial KPIs]								
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [f] market readiness]	4.2800	.84261	4.4400	.71181	4.4400	.65064	4.0400	1.05987
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [g] start-up revenues]	4.0000	.95743	4.1600	.89815	4.2400	.77889	3.8000	1.15470
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process	3.9167	.88055	4.0800	.81240	4.2400	.77889	3.9200	1.25565

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management? [h] number of new business models]								
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [a] pollution control, waste reduction, and recycling]	3.6000	1.08012	3.7200	1.33915	4.5600	.65064	3.9600	1.27410
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [b] energy efficiency and renewable energy]	3.6400	1.03602	3.8800	1.09240	4.5600	.65064	3.8800	1.30128
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [c] sustainable agriculture and biodiversity conservation]	3.6800	.94516	4.2800	.97980	4.2000	.91287	3.8800	1.20139

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13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [d] social inclusion and ethical practices]	3.6400	1.11355	3.7200	1.10000	3.9600	.88882	3.9200	1.15181
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [e] public transport improvement and emission reduction]	4.0400	.93452	3.9600	.97809	4.0000	1.19024	3.8800	1.26886
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [f] climate action]	3.6400	1.18603	3.4400	1.41657	4.1600	1.02794	3.8000	1.32288
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that	3.8800	1.05357	4.3600	.95219	4.4000	.95743	4.0800	1.22202

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sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [g] education for sustainability]									
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Source: Authors' presentation

The analysis of the results based on the respondents' gender is presented in the next table. For the great number of variables, the average ratings given by women are higher than average ratings given by men (nearly 80% variables were rated higher from the women point of view). Only the 19 variables received higher average ratings from men compared to women. The most of them are in the following groups of questions: 2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? (especially for the options: f) R&D centers (4.09 rating from women and 4.17 rating from men) and g) Entrepreneurs (4.42 rating from women and 4.43 rating from men)); 3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? (especially for the options: e) prototyping (4.30 rating from women and 4.34 rating from men), and f) testing (4.42 rating from women and 4.43 rating from men), 4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? (especially for the options: a) design thinking (4.21 rating from women and 4.24 rating from men) and c) rapid prototyping (3.94 rating from women and 4.10 rating from men)), 7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? (especially for the options: b) lack of financing (4.42 rating from women and 4.46 rating from men), e) weak global market connections (4.21 rating from women and 4.40 rating from men), f) lack of entrepreneurial culture (4.09 rating from women and 4.34 rating from men)), 10. How 4 are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? (especially for the options: e) innovation culture (4.48 rating from women and 4.51 rating from men) and g) long-term vision (4.36 rating from women and 4.52 rating from men)), 12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? (especially for the options: a) number of start-ups (3.79 rating from women and 3.91 rating from men), b) attracted investments (4.18 rating from women and 4.28 rating from men), c) jobs created (4.21 rating from women and 4.31 rating from men), f) market readiness (4.15 rating from women and 4.37 rating from men), g) start-up revenues (4.03 rating from women and 4.06 rating from men), h) number of new business models (3.97 rating from women and 4.07 rating from men)).

Table 9: Average ratings according to gender of the respondents

Gender	Female		Male	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [a] flexibility and adaptability]	4.6061	.82687	4.4478	.78400
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [b] collaboration and knowledge sharing]	4.6970	.68396	4.5522	.74434

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1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [c] supportive policy and innovation culture]	4.5758	.83030	4.2537	.91027
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [d] creativity and multidisciplinary approach]	4.5758	.70844	4.4179	.87298
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [e] global connectivity]	4.3333	.77728	4.3284	.87712
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [f] cooperation among stakeholders]	4.4545	.86930	4.2836	.81289
1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem? [g] systematic financial support]	4.3333	.92421	4.2388	1.01637
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [a] start-ups]	4.2424	.83030	4.1940	.92505
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [b] investors]	4.5455	.90453	4.5224	.72526
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [c] academia]	4.1818	1.04447	3.9242	.80976
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [d] government]	4.0909	1.07132	3.7015	1.10117
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [e] accelerators]	4.1212	.99240	3.9701	1.07267
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [f] R&D centers]	4.0909	1.07132	4.1791	.90328
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [g] entrepreneurs]	4.4242	1.00095	4.4328	.82064
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [h] industry leaders]	4.3030	.84723	4.2836	.81289
2. How significant are the following actors of an innovation ecosystem? [i] innovative companies]	4.6667	.77728	4.5821	.65480
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [a] opportunity identification]	4.6667	.64550	4.5075	.63659
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [b] market research]	4.5455	.75378	4.4030	.73977
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [c] idea generation and evaluation]	4.5152	.75503	4.1642	.89776
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [d] concept development]	4.6364	.69903	4.3134	.83863

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3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [e] prototyping]	4.3030	.84723	4.3433	.70823
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [f] testing]	4.4242	.96922	4.4328	.65653
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [g] launching]	4.4545	.83258	4.4179	.67755
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management? [h] feedback analysis]	4.6970	.68396	4.6716	.56106
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [a] design thinking]	4.2121	1.05349	4.2388	.76057
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [b] business model canvas]	4.0606	.89928	3.9104	.82996
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [c] rapid prototyping]	3.9394	.96629	4.1045	.76146
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [d] brainstorming]	4.3636	.96236	4.3284	.80506
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [e] market research]	4.5758	.90244	4.4328	.72245
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [f] MVP testing]	4.3636	.89506	4.2537	.85888
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice? [g] simulations]	4.4545	.90453	4.1343	.86857
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [a] resource efficiency and renewable resources]	4.3030	1.07485	4.0149	.97689
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [b] minimal waste and circular economy]	4.2121	1.13901	3.8955	1.00203
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [c] environmental responsibility and social impact]	4.3030	1.07485	4.0149	.94536
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [d] adaptability]	4.3939	.89928	4.4328	.78284
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [e] green technologies and emission reduction]	4.2727	.94448	3.7612	1.15588
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation? [f] positive economic impact]	4.3333	.95743	4.3134	.76295
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [a] ethical principles]	4.3333	.92421	4.1045	.92334
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [b] transparency and inclusiveness]	4.4848	.87039	3.9403	.96735

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6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [c] social accountability]	4.5455	.86930	3.9851	.89599
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [d] long-term societal benefits]	4.6364	.82228	4.2090	.87969
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [e] community engagement]	4.3939	.93339	3.8209	.91990
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation? [f] minimizing negative impacts]	4.4848	.87039	4.0448	.92822
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [a] lack of infrastructure]	4.4848	.90558	4.2687	.72993
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [b] lack of financing]	4.4242	.86712	4.4627	.70342
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [c] lack of public awareness]	4.3030	.91804	4.1045	.95559
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [d] regulatory barriers and complex regulations]	4.3939	.93339	4.2687	.88046
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [e] weak global market connections]	4.2121	.92728	4.4030	.73977
7. How significant are the following challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country? [f] lack of entrepreneurial culture]	4.0909	.97991	4.3433	.82668
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [a] joint research projects]	4.2727	.91079	4.0896	.86570
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [b] knowledge transfer and shared education]	4.5455	.83258	4.3284	.85967
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [student internships]	4.2424	1.03169	4.0597	.88558
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [c] skill improvement]	4.5758	.79177	4.2836	.81289
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [d] leveraging research capacities]	4.3939	.89928	4.2687	.77032
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [e] market connections]	4.3636	.82228	4.3134	.78256
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [f] technological solutions]	4.4848	.93946	4.3284	.82367

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8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration? [g] innovative programs]	4.3939	1.19738	4.4328	.74313
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [a] universities]	4.2727	1.00849	4.2239	.99728
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [b] companies]	4.6667	.98953	4.5672	.65653
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [c] innovation hubs]	4.4242	.90244	4.2090	.89675
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [d] accelerators]	4.3636	.92932	4.0448	1.06505
9. How significant are the following actors in A2B collaboration? [e] policymakers]	4.2121	1.02340	4.0299	1.14111
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [a] clear strategy]	4.5152	.90558	4.3284	.72589
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [b] intellectual property management]	4.1212	.96039	4.0000	.83485
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [c] transparency]	4.5455	.86930	4.0455	1.02929
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [d] educational programs]	4.5152	.87039	4.2239	.73487
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [e] innovation culture]	4.4848	.87039	4.5075	.65996
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [f] research incubators]	4.4242	.90244	4.1791	.88635
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models? [g] long-term vision]	4.3636	1.02525	4.5224	.63623
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [a] legal regulations]	4.3333	.92421	3.9403	1.05716
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [b] social impact]	4.1212	1.02340	3.8657	.86857
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [c] innovation capacity]	4.3939	.93339	4.2239	.73487
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [d] trust]	4.4848	.87039	4.2537	.82284

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11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [e) government incentives]	4.2424	1.09059	3.9091	.92366
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [f) education]	4.4848	.93946	4.3134	.82036
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [g) transparent communication]	4.6061	.86384	4.2537	.72495
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation? [h) infrastructure]	4.5152	.87039	4.4030	.67554
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [a) number of start-ups]	3.7879	.99240	3.9104	1.01102
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [b) attracted investments]	4.1818	1.01411	4.2836	.81289
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [c) jobs created]	4.2121	1.02340	4.3134	.78256
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [d) number of innovations]	4.1818	1.04447	4.1343	.86857
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [e) financial KPIs]	4.2424	.96922	4.0597	.77617
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [f) market readiness]	4.1515	.97215	4.3731	.75550
12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [g) start-up revenues]	4.0303	1.07485	4.0597	.90253

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12. How significant are the following indicators for assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management? [h) number of new business models]	3.9697	1.13150	4.0758	.84691
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [a) pollution control, waste reduction, and recycling]	4.2424	1.06155	3.8209	1.19247
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [b) energy efficiency and renewable energy]	4.1515	1.17583	3.9104	1.04056
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [c) sustainable agriculture and biodiversity conservation]	4.1212	1.11124	3.9552	.99137
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [d) social inclusion and ethical practices]	4.2727	1.00849	3.5821	1.01726
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [e) public transport improvement and emission reduction]	4.3030	1.07485	3.8060	1.06228
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [f) climate action]	4.2121	1.16613	3.5373	1.24716
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country? [g) education for sustainability]	4.3636	1.14067	4.0896	1.01102

Source: Authors' presentation